

POLICY CONFERENCE

UNLOCKING CIRCULARITY AND
MARKET POTENTIAL FROM WOOD WASTE
25 MARCH 2026, BRUSSELS

VIEWS OF A MAJOR PANEL PRODUCER

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TURNOVER

~841M€

EMPLOYEES

~2600

NATIONALITIES

38

PRODUCTION CAPACITY

3,9M M³

31%

OF THE WOOD USED IN 2025 WAS RECYCLED

SUSTAINABILITY

is at the core of our vision:
to create wood-based solutions for a better life, a better future and a better planet

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**RECYCLING
CENTERS**

- > **1990s**
We were pioneers in the usage of recycled wood
- > **80%**
Recycled wood incorporated in our PB range
- > **9.3%**
increase in the share of recycled wood used by 2029
Recycled wood consumption in thousand dry tons / total wood consumption in thousand dry tons (%), baseline year: 2021.
- > **25M€**
Recycling and wood efficiency investments 2024-2026

From “non-recyclable” to “technically possible”:

- **EcoReFibre** industrial pilots and demonstrations show that **MDF can be recycled back into fibers and reused in new panels**
- **Multiple recycling** routes exist (dry and wet fiber-to-fiber processes)
- **MDF fibers can be recovered** from:
 - raw MDF
 - coated MDF
 - mixed wood waste streams
- Recycled fibers are shorter — but **mechanical performance can be achieved with process adaptation**
- **Industrial feasibility has been demonstrated**, not just lab success

If technology works, why isn't circular MDF everywhere?

Feedstock quality

- Post-consumer wood waste is heterogeneous
- Contamination, coatings, mixed materials

Infrastructure gap

- Collection, sorting, and pre-treatment are uneven or missing
- Circularity fails before the factory gate

Economics

- Recycled fibers still struggle to compete with virgin wood
- Circular solutions carry extra cost without market reward
- Benefits (CO₂ savings, resource efficiency) are not monetised
- Investment

EU Policy is ambitious – but not yet enabling

No strong pull for recycled content in products

Incineration and landfill still compete economically

Create market pull

Incentives or requirements for recycled content
Reward avoided CO₂ and resource savings

Design for future circularity

Products and resins that anticipate a second life
Circularity by design, not by exception

Align environmental goals with industrial reality

Stable, predictable frameworks that justify investment

Enable scale, not only innovation

Support industrial roll-out, not just pilot projects

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